

Relationship Structure - Activity. Phenolic Group and Aromatic Electron- Withdrawing Effect of Substituents as Pharmacophores for the Antipyretic Activity

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ABSTRACT

2-Hydroxy-5-nitro benzoic acid **1** has been synthesized from acetyl salicylic acid known as aspirin. The synthesized compound has been characterized using proton, carbon-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance data. The evaluation of its *in vivo* antipyretic activities above the Wistars rats shows that the derivative **1** is most active than its analogue aspirin. The derivative **1** shows an average temperature decrease of 1,4°C at the minimal concentration of 0,125 mol/l against *Plasmodium bergeri* inoculated to the Wistars rats, whereas aspirin doesn't show any activity under the same conditions. The higher antipyretic activity of the derivative **1** is explained by the pharmacophore character of the phenolic group reinforced with intramolecular H-bonds and the aromatic electron-withdrawing effect of substituents.

Keywords: Aspirin derivative, higher *in vivo* antipyretic activity, phenolic group, electron-withdrawing substituents, pharmacophores for antipyretic activity.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, it proves that the most of pathologies have as major symptoms the pain, the temperature increase and the inflammation¹. In such circumstance, the first reaction of the patient consists to turn to the antipyretic and analgesic drugs such as aspirin, paracetamol, ibuprofene, phenacetin,... In the range of the used drugs for fighting these symptoms, aspirin is one of the drugs, which has a broad spectrum of activities. It is one of the drugs that the patients can get and take easily.

However, the activity of aspirin is limited; especially as some diseases like HIV/AIDS, Ebola discovered during the second half of the twentieth century exhibit symptoms of strong fever causing the precocious death of a lot of patients.

In the aim to find different pharmacophore groups for improving the antipyretic activity of these drugs, we have thought to proceed if possible via structural modifications of these antipyretic drugs by synthesis and to subject the obtained products to *in vivo* antipyretic screening above the Wistars rats inoculated of the *Plasmodium bergeri*. It is in this frame that we have synthesized the compound **1** from aspirin through a nitration by aromatic electrophile substitution followed of the hydrolysis of the ester group. This synthesis has been accompanied of the *in vivo* evaluation of its antipyretic activities above the Wistars rats inoculated of the *Plasmodium bergeri* and expressed by the average temperature variation before and after the inoculation of the *Plasmodium bergeri* in the Wistars rats.

The determination of the mechanism of action of the aspirin has incited the researchers to find the aspirin – like compounds whose the inhibition on the prostaglandins could be identical; it means general or more specific². In this inhibition activity, the carboxylic acid group is an important pharmacophore². The discovery of other pharmacophore groups for improving the antipyretic activity remains an important contribution of this work.

Synthesis of 2-Hydroxy-5-nitro benzoic acid **1**

Aspirin derivate **1** has been obtained by a modified synthesis method proposed by L.F. Tietze and T. Eicher³. The nitration was carried out using the mixture of concentrated nitric acid and concentrated sulfuric acid in equivalent volume at lower temperature (below 10°C). This reaction was accompanied of an acid hydrolysis of the ester group. The addition of NaOH to pH 4-5, which is the usual pH of aspirin, led up after recrystallization with acetone-water to get the derivative **1** as yellow crystals. The chemical equation can be summarized in this manner as illustrated in the scheme 1:

Scheme 1

EXPERIMENTAL PART

TLC: aluminium sheets silicagel (60 F254 Merck).

¹H- and ¹³C-NMR spectra: Bruker Avance 300 (300 and 75 MHz, resp.), tetramethylsilane and CD₃COCD₃ with respect to TMS as internal references; δ in ppm and J in Hz.

2-Hydroxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid (1). To a stirred mixture of 45.5 ml (1.1 mol) concentrated nitric acid and 45.5 ml (1.1 mol) concentrated sulfuric acid at -10°C were added 25 g (0.4 mol) of aspirin by portion of 1g all three minutes. The solution was stirred for 2h and kept at a temperature inferior to 20°C. After 2h, the solution was poured in 300 g ice for precipitating the formed product; and a solution of 3N NaOH was then added until pH 4-5, which is the usual pH of aspirin. The resulting precipitate was filtered and washed with distilled water. The solid residue was at last dried and recrystallized with acetone-water: **1** was isolated (13.1g, 51.5%) as yellow crystals.

¹H-NMR: Table 1. ¹³C-NMR: Table 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical results

The progress of the reaction for obtaining aspirin derivate **1** has been monitored by thin layer chromatography. Aspirin shows an R_f value of 0,63, whereas its derivate **1** has an R_f value of 0,52 with ethyl acetate as eluent. This led us up to confirm that there has been effectively a reaction which has given a product whose the structure is fully supported by ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR data.

Table 1. ¹H-NMR Data (CD₃COCD₃) of the aspirin derivate **1** at 300 MHz; δ in ppm and J in Hz, internal standard TMS.

H-C (6)	8.75
H-C (4)	8.42
H-C (3)	7.20
OH	3.72
J (6.4)	2.7
J (4.3)	9.2
J (4.6)	2.7
J (3.4)	9.3

Table 2. ¹³C-NMR Data (CD₃COCD₃) of the aspirin derivate **1** at 75 MHz; δ in ppm, internal standard TMS

C (1')	170.77
C (2)	166.70
C (5)	139.90
C (6)	130.35
C (4)	126.47
C (1)	118.40
C (3)	112.78

Table 3 : Average balance sheet of different doses for acetyl salicylic acid and 2-Hydroxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid **1**.

Administered doses	Concentration (mol/l)	Number of Wistars rats	Used substances	T _{mai} (°C)	T _{mpi} (°C)	T _{apt} (°C)	ΔT _m (°C)
1000 mg/kg weight of rat	0.500	3	AP	36.0±0.1	37.0±0.1	35.9±0.1	1.1
		3	APD	35.4±0.1	37.1±0.1	35.4±0.1	1.7

In comparing the ¹H-NMR data of the aspirin derivate **1** and the aspirin, we observe the presence of three protons in the aromatic part (7ppm-9ppm) of the derivate **1**, whereas the aspirin one gets four protons.

The ³J coupling constant between two protons amounts to around 9 Hz in the compound **1**. A coupling constant of 2.7 Hz for the proton (6) at 8.75 ppm shows that this proton knows a distant coupling. This proves the absence of a neighbouring proton, and consequently the introduction of another group apart from the proton in the aromatic part of the derivate **1**. Thus, this introduction of the nitro group in the position (5) must lead up the protons (4) and (6) to the higher chemical shifts, respectively to 8.42 ppm and 8.75 ppm in the derivate **1** in comparison with those of aspirin (7.39 ppm and 8.07 ppm). It is also to observe the absence of the proton (5) in the derivate **1**.

All this leads up to confirm that there has been a nitration reaction by electrophile aromatic substitution. This nitration is favoured in the position (5) owing to the sterically hindered position (3). We know also that the nitro group is a bulky group and requires a big space for its site. Moreover, the proton (3) near to the electron-donor OH group is to find in a highfield shift (7.20 ppm), and we also observe the removal of the protons of methyl group at the lower chemical shifts of the ¹H-NMR spectrum of the aspirin derivate **1**.

The interpretation of the ¹³C-NMR spectrum of the aspirin derivate **1** shows that the carbon of the carboxyl group and the carbon of the methyl group, both in the acetyl group of aspirin, remain absents in this spectrum. This proves enough the removal of the acetyl group in the aspirin derivate **1** and confirms that the nitration was accompanied of the hydrolysis reaction. This reaction can be explained by the reversibility of the esterification and saponification reactions⁴. In our case, the saponification takes place as an acid catalyzed reaction because of the higher concentration of water according to Le Chatelier's principle.

In vivo antipyretic Tests

After the determination of the structure of the synthesized product **1**, the *in vivo* antipyretic activities of the derivate **1** have been evaluated in relation to one of the aspirin. 2-Hydroxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid **1** and aspirin have been evaluated for their antipyretic activities above the Wistars rats grown at the Institut National des Recherches biomédicales/ Kinshasa, DRC and inoculated of the *Plasmodium bergeri*. Different doses have been administered to the different Wistars rats, and the antipyretic activities have been expressed by the average temperature variation before and after the inoculation of the *Plasmodium bergeri* to the Wistars rats (Table 3). The temperature has been measured 3 hours after the treatment with aspirin or aspirin derivate **1**, because this time corresponds to the half-life of the aspirin after its administration in the body⁵.

500 mg/kg weight of rat	0.250	3	AP	35.4±0.1	37.0±0.1	35.6±0.1	1.4
		3	APD	36.1±0.1	37.3±0.1	35.1±0.1	2.2
250 mg/kg weight of rat	0.125	3	AP	35.6±0.1	37.1±0.1	37.1±0.1	≈ 0
		3	APD	36.1±0.1	37.2±0.1	35.8±0.1	1.4

Symbols

-T_{mai} (°C): Average temperature of the rat before the inoculation of *Plasmodium bergeri*;

-T_{mpi} (°C): Average temperature of the rat after the inoculation of *Plasmodium bergeri*;

-T_{apt} (°C): Average temperature of the rat after the administration of aspirin or aspirin derivate **1** at a good determined concentration;

-ΔT_m (°C): Average temperature variation (T_{apt}-T_{mpi});

-AP: aspirin;

-APD: aspirin derivate **1**

From the table 3, we observe that the aspirin derivate **1** shows an higher *in vivo* antipyretic activity than aspirin at the same concentration. This is remarkable at the minimal concentration of 0.125 mol/l, where the temperature decrease amounts to 1.4 °C for the aspirin derivate **1**, whereas aspirin doesn't show any activity. Indeed, the different mechanisms of action of aspirin have in common the blocking of the production of prostaglandins as Vane and Piper have suggested it⁶. For the inhibition of prostaglandin, one of the important methods of action is the uncoupling of oxidative phosphorylation in cartilaginous and hepatic mitochondria by diffusing from the inner membrane space as a proton carrier back into the mitochondrial matrix, where it ionizes once again to release protons⁷. In short, aspirin buffers and transports the protons, acting as a competitor to ATP synthase. This leads up to the inhibition of cyclooxygenase, the enzyme responsible for converting arachidonic acid into prostaglandin⁸. From this method of action, we can observe that the release of protons is linked at the antipyretic activity. Thus, we can explain the higher antipyretic activity for the aspirin derivate **1** on the one hand by the presence of an electron-withdrawing substituent like the nitrogroup on the aromatic ring, that increase the acidity of phenolic group by stabilizing the phenolate group by resonance⁹, and on the other hand by the existence of intramolecular H-bonds (OH..... O=C) between the OH group and the carbonyl group of the carboxylic acid function, that increase the acidity of the aspirin derivate **1** too^{9,10}. We can also add the cooperative effect of the both electron-withdrawing substituents (-COOH, -NO₂). These different effects contribute towards a pK_a value of 2.28 for the aspirin derivate **1**, whereas the one of the nearby structures like salicylic acid, m-nitrobenzoic acid and p-nitrophenol amount respectively to 2.98, 3.45 and 7.15¹¹. After examining those pK-values, we can say that the presence of phenolic group next to that of electron-withdrawing substituents are important pharmacophores in antipyretic activity. We think that this is a reason of the use of paracetamol (p-hydroxyacetanilid), that contains a phenolic group, instead of phenacetin (p-ethoxyacetanilid) for the decrease of corporal temperature in case of fever¹⁰. The use of electron-donor substituents in these compounds can be explained by the concern for decreasing of the acidity of these drugs or for the facility of its assimilation in the body. Electron-withdrawing substituents are not only to find in

aspirin, but also in other antipyretic drugs like ibuprofen, noramidopyrine known as dipyrone...

Despite that the toxicological properties of the aspirin derivate **1** have not been fully investigated and the higher acidity of this compound¹¹, this study has allowed us to find some pharmacophore groups for the antipyretic activity.

CONCLUSION

From the synthesis of 2-Hydroxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid **1**, that we can not perhaps used directly owing to its acidity and its toxicological properties that have not been fully investigated, we have been able to determine some pharmacophores for the antipyretic activity. We note the phenolic group reinforced with intramolecular H-bonds and the electron-withdrawing substituents fixed on the aromatic ring. With these pharmacophores, we can reach to design new structures with higher antipyretic activities, and to obtain them through good oriented syntheses.

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